

A STUDY OF COMPUTER PHOBIA AMONG SCHOOL TEACHERS TEACHING IN SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN RELATION TO THEIR MARITAL STATUS

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Abstract

The computer phobia of senior secondary school teacher teaching in senior secondary school in Himachal Pradesh research was conducted by the researcher. The sample was collected from teachers teaching in senior secondary schools of Mandi and Kullu Distt. of Himachal Pradesh. The study was confined to a sample of 400 teachers. The study was restricted to two variables i.e. computer phobia as dependent variable and marital status is independent variables. In the present study Computer Phobia Scale constructed and standardized by Dr. Rajasekar and Dr. Vaiyapuri Raja was used by the researcher. Statistics is a mathematical technique or process of gathering, describing, organizing, analysis and interpreting numerical data. The statistical techniques are used to give meaningful and consider picture of the whole data so that it could be easily comprehended. It is employed to test the hypotheses in the study. In order to study the distribution of computer phobia scores of secondary school teachers, descriptive statistics like mean, median, mode, S.D. ,Q.D., skewness and kurtosis was used. For studying the marital status-wise, significance of the difference in the computer phobia among school teachers teaching in senior secondary schools, t-test was used and the investigator find that there was no

significant difference in the mean scores of overall computer phobia of married and unmarried school teachers teaching in senior secondary schools.

Introduction: Computer has revolutionized the education field. In the present progressive era having computer knowledge practically is too much necessary. But there are many persons who fear to perform on computer; this is known as computer phobia. There is no consensus in the literature on the use of the terms such as computer anxiety, computer phobia and technophobia. In the studies performed so far this subject has been handled under some titles, computer phobia, techno stress, cyberphobia, computer aversion, technophobia, and computer anxiety. Although technophobia is becoming a commonly used term, appearing in newspapers and popular magazines with increasing frequency, in a pioneering work, defined computer phobia as: (a) a resistance to talking about computers or even thinking about computers, (b) fear or anxiety toward computers, and (c) hostile or aggressive thoughts about computers. Afterwards, technophobia has come to be known as computer phobia, and has been defined as: “(a) anxiety about present or future interactions with computers or computer related technology, (b) negative global attitudes about computers, and their operation or their societal impact; and/or, (c) specific negative cognitions or self-critical internal dialogues during actual computer interaction or when contemplating future computer interaction.”

Computer phobia is an intense fear of something that possesses little of no danger. While people with computer phobia realize that these fears are irrational, they often find that facing or even thinking about facing the fear situation brings on a panic attack. One of the root causes of computer phobia is the rapidity of technological advance. In the present technological society, the impression is that artifacts such as computers are more valued than people. Thus, computer phobia is a particularly striking example of the effects of the rapid growth of a technological society.

Abd-Hamid, Yong, Chua, (2003) examined Computer phobia among students in three streams. Descriptive survey method was used in this study. A sample of Malaysian undergraduate students was selected. After the analysis of data it was found that science students have the lowest level of computer phobia, followed by social science and then arts students.

Alaba and Biodun (2003) conducted a study to investigate the extent to which computer efficacy, computer use and Computer Phobia could predict the level of student's 57 academic performance in computer graphics course. The study adopted the descriptive research design. A

total of 189 undergraduates of Olabisi Onabanjo University, Nigeria, served as sample for the study. The results of this indicate that computer use and efficacy significantly play role in reducing phobia towards accomplishing given academic tasks via the computer.

Yadav, Reena (2004); In her paper titled Attitude of Secondary School Teachers Towards The Use of Information Communication Technology In Education determined the attitude of educators from secondary school for implementation of ICT in educational sector. The study's main intents were to investigate the attitudes of female and male teachers, educators from schools belonging to urban and rural localities, educators from various sectors namely government and public toward ICT usage in educational sector. In the study, the researcher employed the descriptive survey method of research. Purposive random sampling was utilised, and the sample was drawn in phases. In the first stage, 200 educators from secondary level school were chosen based on gender (80 males and 120 females), area (100 rural and 100 urban), organisation (100 private and 100 government), followed by age (95 above 40 and 105 below 40). In the study, an ICT Attitude Scale (self-developed) was employed as a tool. According to the conclusions of her study, female instructors had more pragmatic perspective towards ICT usage than male teachers. Teachers at private schools had more pragmatic perspective towards ICT usage in educational sector than teachers in public 31 schools. Teachers under the age of 40 have a more positive attitude toward the use of ICT in education than teachers over the age of 40 in secondary school. Mona, Samriti; The study's goal is to discover secondary school teachers' aversion to computer use. a sample of 30 teachers was collected from secondary schools using a simple random technique total 10 schools out of which 30 teachers took part in the survey including 15 males and 15 female teachers between the age group of 25 to 50 years sample consists of inservice teachers of government schools the researcher used computer phobia scale 2010 by Dr. S Rajasekar and Dr.P.vaiyapuri. She observed that majority of educators have a moderately low level of computer phobia. Only 22% of the sample thinks that they encounter no issues comprehending the technicalities related to computers, and 39% agree that they favourably accomplish various computer aided work daily. The majority of teachers are enthusiastic about using computers for personal purposes. More over 60% of teachers stated that they not only enjoy working with computers, but that they also feel confident doing so. Some factors where teachers received negative scores lead to the conclusion that many teachers are sceptical of the use of computers in educational practise. Furthermore, it was discovered that

teaching experience and gender are substantially connected with instructors' beliefs and perceptions of computer use.

Rajasekar and Sini (2005) studied 'Internet Knowledge of Research Scholars.' The objectives of the study were to find out the internet knowledge of research scholars of various subjects in Kerala University and to assess the differences across different categories of scholars based on their residence, gender, and faculty. The investigator has used normative survey method in the study. The investigator constructed and validated an internet knowledge test. It consisted of 30 multiple choice questions needed 30 minutes for answering. Mean and standard deviation of the internet knowledge scores of the entire sample and sub-sample were computed and the results indicated that the internet knowledge of entire sample was relatively high (mean=16.25). The male research scholars had relatively high internet knowledge than the female research scholars. The internet knowledge of research scholar belonging to science subjects was relatively high (mean=18.74). The investigator found that there no significance difference between urban and rural research scholars of various subjects of science subjects.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM: The problem selected for research may be defined as under.

“A STUDY OF COMPUTER PHOBIA AMONG SCHOOL TEACHERS TEACHING IN SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN RELATION TO THEIR MARRITAL STATUS”

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY: The study was conducted to achieve the following objectives.

1. To study marital status-wise difference in computer phobia among school teachers teaching in senior secondary schools with respect to:
 - i. Personal Failure
 - ii. Human Vs. Machine Ambiguity
 - iii. Convenience

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

In the present study following hypotheses were formulated.

1. There will be no significant marital status-wise difference in computer phobia among school teachers teaching in senior secondary schools with respect to:
 - i. Personal Failure
 - ii. Human Vs. Machine Ambiguity

iii. Convenience

DELIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The present study was delimited to the following aspects.

- ❖ The sample included only schoolteachers teaching in senior secondary schools of Mandi and Kullu Distt. of Himachal Pradesh.
- ❖ The study was confined to a sample of 400 teachers.
- ❖ The study was restricted to two variables i.e., computer phobia as dependent variable and marital status-wise, independent variables.

OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS OF TERMS USED

Following terms have been used in the study.

- 1. Computer Phobia:** Computer phobia is a fear or dislike of advanced technology. It invokes a wide range of negative emotions, such as anxiety, incompetence, fear, stress and nervousness. It not only creates psychological imbalances but shifts human nature from reality. In the present study the level of computer phobia among teachers was assessed by 'Computer Phobia Scale' developed and standardized by Dr. S. Rajasekar and Dr. P. Vaiyapuri.
- 2. Senior Secondary School Teachers:** It refers to the teachers teaching in government senior secondary schools of Distt. Kullu and Mandi of Himachal Pradesh.
- 3. Marital Status:** married and unmarried teachers teaching in senior secondary schools

RESEARCH METHOD USED

In order to accomplish the objective of the present study, the descriptive survey method was considered appropriate for gathering data computer phobia among secondary school teachers. Descriptive survey method is designed to obtain pertinent and precise information concerning the status of phenomena and whenever possible to draw valid general conclusions from the facts discovered. Descriptive research involves events that present conditions. It aims to describe "what exists" with respect to variables or conditions or conditions in a situation.

SAMPLING: Some populations are so large that their study would be expansive in terms of time, money, efforts, and manpower. Sampling is one of the most important and indispensable factors of every research study. Sampling is a process by which a relatively small number of individuals, objects or events are selected and analyzed in order to find out something about the target population from which the representative sample was selected. Sampling has been increasingly used in educational research for answering certain questions about a specific

population. The sample drawn out of population should be true representative of the population otherwise; the results of the study may turn to be futile. The representative proportion of the population is called a sample.

In the present investigation, a representative sample of 400 school teachers teaching in senior secondary schools was selected from district Mandi and Kullu of Himachal Pradesh by using convenient sampling technique.

TOOL USED: In the present study Computer Phobia Scale constructed and standardized by Dr. Rajasekar and Dr. Vaiyapuri Raja was used by the researcher.

DATA ANALYSIS: Statistics is a mathematical technique or process of gathering, describing, organizing, analysis and interpreting numerical data. The statistical techniques are used to give meaningful and consider picture of the whole data so that it could be easily comprehended. It is employed to test the hypotheses in the study. In order to study the distribution of computer phobia scores of secondary school teachers, descriptive statistics like mean, median, mode, S.D., Q.D., skewness and kurtosis was used. For studying the gender-wise, significance of the difference in the computer phobia among school teachers teaching in senior secondary schools, t-test was used.

CONCLUSIONS: From the analysis and interpretation of the data, following conclusions may be drawn.

There is no significant marital status-wise difference in the mean scores of Personal Failure component of computer phobia among senior secondary school teachers.

Marital Status-wise Difference among Senior Secondary School Teachers in Terms of Personal Failure

❖ There is no significant marital status-wise difference in the mean scores of Human Vs. Machine Ambiguity component of computer phobia among senior secondary school teachers.

Marital Status-wise Difference among Senior Secondary School Teachers in Terms of Human Vs Machine Ambiguity

❖ There is no significant marital status-wise difference in the mean scores of Convenience component of computer phobia among senior secondary school teachers.

Marital Status-wise Difference among Senior Secondary School Teachers in Terms of Convenience

- ❖ There is no significant difference in the mean scores of overall computer phobia among married and unmarried senior secondary school teachers.

Marital Status-wise Difference among Senior Secondary School Teachers in Terms of Overall Computer Phobia

EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATIONS

The results of the present study have following implications for education:

- Teacher trainees are suggested to take computer knowledge as an essential part of their study. Only theoretic knowledge is not sufficient for it, they should know practical knowledge of computer also.
- Teachers should be motivated to get training in the use of IT. It can be done with the help of various types of workshops, seminars, orientations programs and refresher courses for teachers which will develop in them positive and favourable attitude towards information technology and computer.
- Individual training should be given through chat base online or web-based therapy which can develop in teachers a positive attitude towards web self-efficacy, perceive web enjoyment, and behavioral intention to use the web in order to remove the phobia.
- Teachers need to be prompted to make use of internet for updating their knowledge and general awareness.

SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER STUDY

A few suggestions for further research having put forward as under

- The study may be conducted by taking sample from other districts of the state.
- A comparative study of computer phobia among tribal and non-tribal school teachers may be done.
- A study can be undertaken to find out the effect of psychological factors on attitude of teachers towards computer and information technology.

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